

Effects Of Time Management On Male Students' Academic Achievement

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Abstract

Time Management plays a key role in success of a person. Relevant literature established that a relationship exists between time management and academic achievement of students. The study focused on undergraduate level. The major purpose of the study was to know about the students' awareness regarding time management and whether they prepare any schedule for their weekly activities. Moreover, it was also aimed to look at whether is there any impact of time management on students' academic achievement. The study considered all public sector universities as population. Four sample universities were conveniently selected in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Random sampling technique was applied to select students in these universities for data collection. Students' time management was calculated by Britton and Tesser scale whereas their semester results were collected from controller of examination office. The collected data was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted in the light of the objectives of the study. Data were analyzed through Chi-Square and Continuity Co-relation. It was found that a strong relationship exists between time management an academic achievement and the p-value was less than 0.05. It was established that good time management score is directly related to better academic score. It was recommended that university teachers may provide proper guidance to students for utilization of their time in order to achieve their academic targets.

Introduction

Intellectuals of different period define the importance of time; Plato measured its standard and rule in the world whereas Aristotle explained the basic scale of measuring motion (Kelly, 2002). Some other scholars considered such a precious source that is provided in the same magnitude to every person in this universe (Ancona et al., 2015). Its dispersal dissemination is in equal amount to all being. These researchers put their view as its use is totally reliant on the person skills. How a person uses this source material a lot? The school heads time management is mainly reliant on various variables such as styles of time management, school category i.e. private or government, school level.

Proper Time Management can lead any institutional head towards better results. Cole (2002) argued that the key to success is completely dependent on proper Time Management, learning ability, coordination and financial arrangement. It has been accepted that Time Management can create simplicity in task achievement according to situation and topic. Working in sequential and systematic way can enhance our performance because time is same for everyone and it is mandatory for us to use it properly. Kelly (2002) clarified that it is frequently a specific tricky and often individuals know about the significance of time application mechanically. He emphasizes that task achievement can only be possible if we schedule proper time for every task.

Britton and Glynn (1989) explain that Time Management involves mostly three basic components which are macro, intermediate and micro. They highlighted that macro level of time management indicates an individual's adoption and objectives importance. Intermediate level is regarded as another factor which can have built the idea of creation and task achievements which are mandatory in first stage. In the third level which is called micro level, all preparation is carried out to implement the already created tasks in the second stage. They formulated a scale about Time Management which focused on these three levels. The form is formulated to study everyone's performance related time management. Furthermore, Conway and Briner (2009) claimed that time management is a person's eccentric qualities and this mannerism is simulated by the individual's how do they operate their time.

Time Management –A Significant Challenge

It was observed that most of the people are consistently performing numerous tasks and complaining about shortage of time. It has been observed that mostly people feel pressure as they face time management issues. It has been noticed that many educationalists knew the significance of time management in educational curriculum (Anchona et al., 2015).

A significant portion of literature suggests that exercise of proper management is verily important for employees. Proper time management is a significant tool to achieve progress in profession and earn more

income. Johnson and Dick (2019) explained that poor time management brings bad results for students and professionals as well.

Background of the Study

At university level, academic achievement and Cumulative Grad Points Average (CGPA) is based on the positive completion assignments which have to be completed in given time. Hence, it is mandatory for the students to complete the assigned tasks within the allocated time frame. Currently, students are faced with manifold responsibilities and social applications dilemma. Iheanacho (2002) concluded that in modern day world, it is a test of a person's ability to manage the time.

Importance of Time Management in academic life in different categories is properly explained by Britton and Tesser (1991). Study by Xu (2015) suggested that academic achievement is influenced by time management skill of the students. It was established that a major factor of students at higher secondary level unsatisfactory results is low management skill (Hijazi, Naqvi & Raza, 2006). Other studies also claimed that an association is found between time consumed in academic activities, studies and accomplishments (Grissom, Loeb and Mitani, 2015). They make it easy for the learners to take interest in their studies and activities which are indirectly related to result.

Debayo (2015) mentioned that it is the common problem for students to manage their time properly that has an association with learners' academic achievement. Prioritization and procrastination are the problem which came to every student in their academic life (Deniz, Tras & Aydogan, 2019). It has been accepted that there are several other problems that students are facing like improper task prioritization and improper allocation of time for tasks. In Pakistan, it is pointed out that students at undergraduate level enter into a new social circle and they do not bother about time proper utilization.

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to know about students' awareness regarding time management and whether they prepare any schedule for their weekly activities. Moreover, it was aimed to look at whether there is any impact of time management on students' academic achievement.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. Time management has no relationship with male students' academic achievement.
2. Students Time management and academic achievement has a positive correlation.

Significance of the Study

The study provides an insight to the teachers, academic institution heads and parents about the proper time management impact on the students' academic achievement. It gives information that students need to learn how to prioritize their tasks according to its importance. It will help them what to be done on immediate basis and what to be postponed. The current research broadens the scope of the research area for other scholars who wish to conduct studies in the same area.

Delimitations of the Study

The study was delimited to undergraduate male students in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Components of Time Management

Lay and Schouwenburg (2016) described that having a decent scheme of activities is necessary and some regard it as a work of a genius. If the adjacent atmosphere is in a disarray, then the focus on the task is less. They further explain that a dull and nasty display and ill prepared schemes are considered as the trap of time. It's an inappropriate place for loading forms, whereas, it is measured a residence where effort is tacit. If you haven't the potential of saying excuse in work will increase your problem in working time. It has been mandatory that you have the ability to know the limitation in your effort and similarly knows denying the undesirable work. Lastly, such kind of individual has sufficient period for his/her or other works.

Academic Achievement

Student achievements are directly related to their interest in study as they get scores in the class quizzes, mid and terminal term examinations. Osa-Edoh and Alutu (2012) claimed that educational success is the restrained skill and accomplishment level of a student in a university, topic or specific assistance (Indreica, Cazan & Truta, 2021). Broadbent and Poon (2015) defined the realization as a performance of one or an assembly when assumed a thought job. In inculcation, representation is frequently allowed as undistinguishable with educational let down or obtaining, in moving out of a duty, development or responsibility. In inculcation, achievement is regularly accessible as identical with academic attainment or obtaining, in running of an obligation, activity or a package.

Procrastination

Rendering to Tice and Baumeister(2018), delay is pronounced as the consequence of postponing or submitting something at a later stage. Their abilities and hardworking can make it possible to achieve the desired position in the required field. However, it has been observed that their demanding timetable of responsibility, their work, some important tasks have to be carried on a priority basis. Most of the time students cannot distinguish between the important tasks and this inevitably loads up pending work schemes over an important period.

Researchers reflect time management ability and boldness as a significant adjustable factor for having influence on learners' abstract achievement. Karim and Mitra (2019) argued that occasionally learners do not provide good time to tuition or twitch their research for inspection at the very previous minute which is the foremost influence that stimulates their results. School children become questioner and start thoughtful for which they have limited time to deal with their academic as well as social engagements. This can make it worst to manage their work in academic career.

Time management is defined as a talent or conduct which makes it possible for the learners to cope with their regular tasks in such a method that suitable time is owed for every task conferring to its significance and resolve. It is careful as a respected feature for students' superior academic reaching. It is further elucidating that it is essential for the students to recognize that to order their jobs according to its magnitude and then they demand to stay focused on these responsibilities. Likewise, Shellenbarger (2009) explained time management as a proficiency or skill that supports the students to establish their sequence of resources successfully. Other studies clarified time management as a procedure or ability which benefits separately to do and realize the tasks results in an efficient manner (Sangirya, Kawatkar, Dutta & Bhosle, 2004).

Studies by Kaushar (2018), Debayo (2015) and Jalagat (2016) suggested that students' proper time management argued that proper use results in their good grades. These scholars described such students as the best in time management. They argued that proper time management is one of the important variables which influence students' academic performances.

Time Management Relationship with Academic Achievement

Mostly the researchers focused on variables such as school environment, availability of various facilities to learners and teachers, teachers' qualification and teaching practices etc while measuring learners' academic performance (Denlinger, 2014). Victoria emphasized that actually time management for the learners and teachers is one of the important variables to assess learners' performance. She reported that setting up a schedule for activities for learners led to a better academic performance of the school. Igem studied learners' time management in practices in relation to their academic performance at school in 2008. Igem's study suggested that in Tanzania, students are not trained or educated about the importance of time management skill which affects their abilities to schedule tasks according to its importance. Consequently, their performance was negatively affected. Even the study suggested that the school managers (heads) were not giving importance to time management factor.

Relationship of time management with academic performance at school level was studied by Bjorvatn and Tungodden (2010) in Tanzania. The study found that a positive relationship was found between the variables. The study found that the learner who spends most of their time in studying and mathematics task under the observation of their teachers is absolutely connected with better performances. Studies regarding time management and its relationship with learners' performance in science subjects, Claessens, Eerde, Rutte and Roe, (2014) found that those learners who are mostly study under the observation of their teachers produce better academic scores as compared with those who mostly study in isolation. Students' better results are due to their study under the guidance of teachers who plan better the tasks according to its importance for them.

Conway and Briner (2009) investigated the relationship of time management by learners with their academic performance at school level in Uganda. It was found that a greater number of schools do not prioritize tasks for the learners whereas some schools execute the plan in proper way. Schools were provided instruction sample for better and timely execution of activities but major number of schools consider it incomprehensible. Moreover, poor time management is related in some schools because they do not follow the proposed timetable. Simonsen et al., (2010) found that a clear and positive impact is found when the students were given a deadline for academic tasks completion. It is evident from the studies of Johnson and Dick (2019) that time management by the learners is linked with students' results at school level.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research nature was survey and its population was undergraduate students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). Four universities were selected conveniently for sampling and their names were Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan, Bacha Khan University Charsadda, University of Swabi and Mardan Women University were selected conveniently among the thirty-seven universities in KP.

Students as a sample of the study were conveniently selected from the departments from these four universities. Total sample of the study was 400. Sample size from these universities varied due to the variation in their total strength of students. The below table explains the respondent's number.

Data was collected through questionnaire because it allows a researcher to collect more information in short and the most suitable tool in survey research (Moser & Katlon, 2017). Britton and Tesser (1991) standard scale were used to measure students' time management efficacy. Students' results were collected from their respective departments' controller of examination offices. Totally four hundred questionnaires were distributed but only 390 were returned to the researcher. The collected information was compiled and tabulated for analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data were tabulated for analysis and SPSS was used for test application. The researcher applied Pearson Chi Square and Linear by Linear association at the 0.05 level of significance.

OBJECTIVE No 1: Students' Perception about Time Management Score

Table No 1: Students classification according to Time Management Scale Questionnaire

S.No	Category	Score On Time Management Scale
1	Excellent Time Management	45-50
2	Fair Time Management	30-44
3	Low Time Management	Below 30

The table explains that students Time Management skill was measured through the Time Management Scale and the results were divided into three groups. Those students whose score was 45 or more than 45 to 50 were considered as Excellent Time Management whereas those whom scored 30 to 44, were put into the category of Fair Time Management. Low Time Management score was less than 30 on the Scale.

Table No 2: Cross Tabulation of Academic Percentage and Time Management Scale Score

Time Management Scale Score		Academic Percentage			Total
		Excellent	Good	Average	
Time Management Scale Score	Excellent Time Management	27	0	0	27
	Fair Time Management	247	82	5	334
	Low Time Management	00	04	25	29
Total		274	86	26	390

The table explains the already mentioned categories, the number of students who are categorized in each group. Moreover, it explains the students Time Management Category and its relationship with their academic performance. It is evident from the table that among the 390 students, 27 are categorized as Excellent Time Management produced excellent academic performance. In Fair Management category, 247 students are counted whereas in Low Time Management, there were 29 students. The table shows a relationship of students' time management score and their academic performance. All the 27 students who were in the Excellent Time Management category had the best academic performance whereas those whom were categorized as Low Time Management were majorly having average academic performance.

OBJECTIVE NO 2: To Find Out Whether the Students Prepare Their Weekly Plan

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.182 ^a	1	.000		

Continuity Correction ^b	14.063	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	15.458	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	15.107	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	390				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 36.32.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

The p-value favors the statement that students prepare their weekly plan for activities. The data shows that male students do not bother too much about planning their weekly activities. The figures for those who prepare their weekly plan and those who do not, are almost same.

Objective No 3: To Find Out Impact of Time Management on Students' Academic Achievement

Chi-Square Tests				
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	
Pearson Chi-Square	35.839 ^a	4		.000
Likelihood Ratio	33.782	4		.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	29.460	1		.000
N of Valid Cases	390			

a. 5 cells (55.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .28.

The table explains indicates a firm link between students' time management and their academic performance. The strong association is shown by the p-value which is less than 0.05. The data reveals that if a student score is high on Time Management Scale so the academic performance is also the best. Those students whose score is low, their academic performance is also low.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It was found that most of the respondents' score on Time Management Scale was 30-44 which indicated that they fall in the category of Fair Time Management. Only twenty-nine students were ranked in the Low Time Management whereas twenty-seven were in the Excellent Time Management category. Time Management Scale score has a strong relationship with the students' academic score, where students' time management scale score is high, their academic percentage was excellent vice versa. Studies by Xu's (2015) findings support these findings and they further stated that students' excellence in time management brings better academic grades while Hijazi, Naqvi and Raza (2006) found that students' bad results at college level are majorly due to poor time management.

The study showed that approximately 50% of the students prepare the plan for their weekly activities. The study found a strong link between the students' score on Time Management Scale and academic score. The strong and positive relationship is indicated by the p-value which is below than 0.05. Students' academic score improved as their score on Time Management Scale improved vice versa. Studies by Razali, S. N. A. M., Rusiman, M. S., Gan, W. S., & Arbin, N. (2018) and Cyril, A. V. (2021) also stated that students' academic performance is positively associated with students' time management.

It was recommended that students maybe guided and suggested to prepare a weekly plan for their activities and schedule as it strongly associated with better academic results. Better Time Management is an important variable to improve students' academic results so academicians are recommended to emphasize time management skill improvement and the process of prioritization. For such purpose, special lectures and workshops may be organized. Scholars are suggested that they may replicate the study at other levels and universities.

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